

INNOVATIVE TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING PRONUNCIATION.**Toshtimerov Xo'jabek Chinteremovich**

Navoi State Pedagogical institute,

English language and literature faculty student

Scientific adviser **Istamova Dilnoza Sadullayevna**

Annotation: This article gives brief information about the ways of innovative teaching English pronunciation. In this article there are given some interesting and useful methods and games.

Key words: pronunciation, bingo, board game, minimal pairs

English is the lingua franca of many countries. The knowledge of English language has become an essential asset that facilitates us to attain a special status in the modern world. Because of some historical factors, English had spread all over the world. Even though it is spread, each country developed its own variety of English. Language is basically a systematic means of communication which uses sounds and symbols. Pronunciation refers to the way in which we sound or speak a particular language. If the main purpose of language is communication, it can be achieved mainly through proper pronunciation. Linguists demonstrated the importance of pronunciation and developed a unique code i.e. IPA (International Phonetic Alphabet) to standardize pronunciation. Proper pronunciation increases the intelligibility of our speech as well as its effectiveness. But unfortunately, this pronunciation hasn't received due importance in the language teaching context. Particularly in countries like India, where English is taught as the second language, more importance is given to written skills and grammar rather than pronunciation. Pronunciation deserves strong attention in the English class, especially in classes which focuses on communication. Poor pronunciation can cause problems in oral communication, no matter, how good a speaker has control on English grammar and vocabulary. In the earlier days, linguists concentrated more on segmental features.

But from the past 25 years, they are also concentrating on the supra segmental aspects in teaching pronunciation.

How do teachers teach pronunciation in the classroom (the teacher's role)

Helping learner to hear: Part of the role of the teacher is to help learners to perceive the sound. Learners will have a strong tendency to hear the sounds of English in terms of the sounds of their native language.

Helping learners to make sounds: Some sounds of English do not occur in other languages. Sometimes learners will be able to imitate the new sound, but if they can't then the teacher needs to be able to give some advices which may help them to make the new sound(s).

Providing feedback: Both the above tasks require the teacher to evaluate learners' performance. Often learners cannot identify by themselves if they have got it right; the teacher must provide them with information about their performance. There are a lot of interesting and useful games in teaching pronunciation. Some are in the following:

Bingo: Make Bingo grids with minimal pairs using vowels or consonants, or pairs of words that are the same except for stress. (See the example near the end of this chapter. The basic rules of Bingo are given there.) For additional practice, students can take turns calling the Bingo words.

Card games: Children's card games like Go Fish and Crazy Eights can be used to practice pronunciation if we make cards with pictures of objects that contain the sounds you want to practice instead of the usual hearts, diamonds, clubs, and spades.

Look here for instructions for basic card games:

Concentration: This is a game played with cards that match up in pairs: A word and its meaning, a picture and its word, etc. The cards are set out upside down. Players take turns choosing two cards to see if they match. If they do, they are left face up and the player gets a point. If they don't match, they're turned upside down

again and the next player chooses two cards. The object of the game is to find as many matching pairs as possible.

Board games: Find or make a game board with spaces leading from the first to the last space. Write questions or instructions on cards or slips of paper. Change the questions to practice different subject matter. Players throw dice, move the indicated number of spaces, choose a card and answer the question. The object of the game is to reach the “finish” square first. Unless you’re teaching young children, be careful about how many games you use. They’re the icing on the cake, not the cake itself. Students will overdose if they have too much.

Using Minimal Pairs

It can be considered as one of a great way to keep the focus on the pronunciation of the words (or just one sound). Most of the time students are not very familiar with linguistics – a minimal pair is a pair of words that differ only in one specific sound. For instance, you can check the words ‘rat’ and ‘rate’. They can be considered as minimal pairs. It is because there is only one vowel sound which makes the pronunciation of the words different. It will also help students to expand their vocabulary.

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